

Measurement of NO₂ concentrations by passive sampling: A laboratory protocol for students in environmental engineering and related fields

Célia Alves and Teresa Nunes

Department of Environment and Planning, Centre for Environmental and Marine
Studies, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

1. Introduction

Air quality can be assessed through continuous monitoring using instruments that provide real-time data. However, automatic air quality monitors are expensive and require frequent maintenance. Consequently, their deployment is often limited, restricting the possibility of simultaneous measurements at multiple locations. Passive samplers, such as diffusion tubes, overcome some of the limitations associated with automatic monitoring systems and are particularly useful for simultaneous deployment at multiple sampling sites, including locations with limited accessibility or frequent power outages. Initially developed for occupational hygiene applications, diffusion tubes have also been successfully applied in outdoor environments. These devices are small, lightweight, often reusable, relatively inexpensive, silent, and do not require an external power source. Their operation is based on the principle of molecular diffusion, whereby pollutants naturally diffuse from an area of higher concentration (the surrounding atmosphere) toward the absorbing medium inside the tube. The samplers are exposed at the selected site for extended periods, typically ranging from one to four weeks, after which they are analyzed in the laboratory to determine the average pollutant concentration over the exposure period. Although passive samplers provide only time-averaged concentrations over relatively long exposure periods, they are highly suitable for spatial assessments, enabling the characterization of concentration variability between locations and facilitating air quality evaluation across multiple sites simultaneously. However, passive samplers do not provide exact real-time concentration values and are unable to capture short-term pollution peaks or episodic events. Therefore, to improve the reliability of the data obtained, passive sampling results should be compared with and validated against measurements from continuous automatic analyzers or reference methods for the target pollutant.

Most passive samplers consist of a cylindrical tube. In the case of NO₂ sampling, the tubes are fitted with two caps, one at each end. Inside one of the caps, a support material impregnated with a chemical absorbing solution is placed to capture the target pollutant. During sampling, the tubes are mounted vertically in suitable holders, with the impregnated cap positioned at the top and the bottom cap removed to allow air circulation through the tube. When deployed outdoors, this vertical configuration also helps prevent rainwater from entering the sampler. The transport of gas molecules through the tube is governed by Fick's First Law of diffusion, which states that the diffusive movement of molecules is driven by the concentration gradient within the system. According to Fick's Law, the unidirectional flux of gas 1 through gas 2 is given by:

$$F_1 = -D_{12} \cdot dC_1/dz$$

where

- F_1 is the gas flow 1 (mol.cm⁻².s⁻¹)
- D_{12} is the diffusion coefficient of gas 1 in gas 2 (cm².s⁻¹)
- C_1 is the concentration of gas 1 in gas 2 (mol.cm⁻³)
- z is the diffusion length (cm)

For a cylinder of length z and cross-sectional area πr^2 with a concentration gradient $(C_1 - C_0)$, the amount Q_1 (mol) of gas 1 transferred along the tube in t (seconds) is:

$$Q_1 = F_1 \cdot \pi r^2 \cdot t$$

$$Q_1 = -D_{12} \cdot \pi r^2 \cdot t \cdot (C_1 - C_0) / z$$

The negative sign can be ignored as it merely indicates that the flow is measured in the direction of the decreasing concentration of gas 1. $(C_1 - C_0) / z$ is the concentration gradient along the tube of length z . If the absorbing solution, used in the removal of gas 1, is effective, then C_0 will be zero. Thus, the average concentration of the pollutant in the air, over the sampling period, is:

$$C = Q \cdot z / (D_{12} \cdot \pi r^2 \cdot t)$$

For NO_2 , the diffusion coefficient in air is $0.154 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Palmer et al., 1976).

1.1 Determination of nitrogen dioxide

The principle of the method used for sampling and quantification of NO_2 is based on the fact that this atmospheric pollutant is absorbed by triethanolamine (TEA) as nitrite ion, which, after extraction, is analyzed by spectrophotometry in the visible range (540 nm). The NO_2 sampler consists of an acrylic tube with a length of 7.1 cm and an internal diameter of 1.1 cm, with machined ends so that the polyethylene caps fit perfectly (Fig. 1). Three steel grids placed in one of the caps serve as supports for the absorption solution (TEA).

In routine practice, a passive sampler consists of a holder with 4 diffusion tubes: one functions as a blank, and the other three are exposed. After the exposure time, extraction, and analysis, the concentration of nitrogen dioxide is calculated based on the average value of the three exposed tubes, after subtracting the blank.

Fig. 1 – Schematic representation, operating principle and installation of passive tubes for sampling NO_2 .

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Impregnation

The preparation of the tubes involves placing three stainless steel mesh pieces side by side in each cap, to which 30 μl of a 1:1 (v/v) solution of triethanolamine in acetone is directly added (Gair et al., 1991; Heal et al., 1999). The meshes are never handled separately from the cap, either during impregnation or analysis. A tube with the cap on one end is immediately sealed with the cap containing the freshly impregnated meshes. To avoid the impregnation solution dripping down the walls of the tube, keep the tubes in a vertical position with the cap containing the meshes facing downward. To facilitate the identification of the cap with the impregnated meshes, mark the outside of the cap.

In this work, prepare a total of 6 tubes: three will serve as blanks, and three for sampling. Place the tubes in a stand, with the cap without the mesh facing down, and fix them on the outside at about 2.5 meters from the ground or in an indoor location, following the instructions of the professor or laboratory technician. Remove the caps without the mesh from three of the tubes and leave them for sampling for two weeks. The other three sealed tubes will be used to determine the average blank levels. After two weeks of exposure, collect the tubes and the stand, and proceed with the analysis.

2.2 Analysis

The analysis procedure follows that described in *Methods for the determination of indoor pollutants* (1993), with some modifications commonly adopted by English laboratories performing this type of analysis (Atkins and Lee, 1995; Atkins et al., 1986). NO_2 is absorbed as nitrite by TEA and is determined by spectrophotometry according to a variation of the Saltzman method. The cap without the mesh is removed, and 5 ml of a combined reagent is added, consisting of 20 parts of a 1% (w/v) solution of sulfanilamide in 2.5% (v/v) orthophosphoric acid and one part of a 0.14% (w/v) solution of N-1-naphthylethylenediamine (NEDA). The tube is then closed again and shaken. After 20 to 30 minutes from the addition of the reagent, the absorbance is read at 540 nm, in a 1 cm cell, with the set of standards used for calibration having been previously read. If the absorbance of any sample exceeds that of the most concentrated standard, dilute the sample by adding 1 ml of sample to 2 ml of the combined reagent. Mix and let the color develop for 20-30 minutes before reading.

The nitrite present reacts with sulfanilamide to form a diazo compound, which, when coupled with NEDA, forms a pink-colored azo compound. The phosphoric acid serves to acidify the medium and allow for rapid and maximum color development (pH 2).

2.3 Preparation of standards

From a sodium nitrite stock solution (1.725 g.l^{-1}), transfer the following volumes into 50 ml flasks using a micropipette: 0.00, 0.125, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, and 1.00 ml. Dilute to the mark with ultra-pure water. Pipette 120 μl of each of the standards previously prepared into 15 (or 20 ml) flasks, properly labeled, add 12 ml of the reagent solution, and shake. Wait for 10-15 minutes. Read the absorbance at 540 nm. Set the spectrophotometer to zero using a reference cell with ultra-pure water.

3. Report

From the calibration curve obtained, calculate the concentration of nitrite/nitrogen dioxide in each of the exposed and blank tubes. The amount of nitrogen dioxide collected (Q) corresponds to the difference between the average nitrite quantities measured in the three exposed sampling tubes and those measured in the three blank tubes.

4. References

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